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DIGITIZATION - AN ESSENTIAL PROCESS OF THE INFORMATION SECURITY AND HUMAN SECURITY SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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Abstract: The modern development of information technologies leads to the need to protect information. In this article were elucidated important aspects of the security of informatics systems and information security, being at the same time argued the necessity of security of information systems, for ensuring human and informational safety.

Keywords: computer system, human security, security of information systems, information security, standard, threat, requirements.

Today, the issue of security, for several obvious reasons, is one of the most discussed among experts and researchers. Of course, the issue of security has always been the focus of the international community and has traditionally been understood as the defence of the territory by military means. However, modern realities force us to abandon militaristic interpretations and for this, there is a rather eloquent explanation. First, this approach does not take into account cultural and emotional factors, as a result, it is impossible to explain a state's decision to start a war. Secondly, the principle of non-intervention in the internal affairs of a state and the large number of threats to humanity cannot coexist peacefully. Third, these approaches are characterized by very low predictive power. The question is to find an alternative to traditional approaches to security. Moreover, such an alternative already exists. This is the concept of human security, which suggests that the person, not the state, should become the main point of reference for security. It should be noted that the idea of human security is not new in its essence.

The scale and consequences of the modern stage of computerization of society have a revolutionary character and cause not only new expectations and hopes for a better future, but also generate illusions and myths. The computerization of society brings new potential threats, and last but not least to the person. In the modern era, it has become axiomatic to say: real power belongs to the one who holds the information, as well as its antithesis: information belongs to the one who holds the real power.

The term "e-democracy" or "digital democracy" has come to be frequently used by those who use computer technology in the political process. The concepts of digital democracy refer to theories that consider computers and / or computer networks as essential tools in the functioning of a democratic political system. "Digital democracy" is any democratic political system in which computers and computer networks are used to perform essential functions of the democratic process, such as disseminating information and communication, uniting the interests of citizens and making decisions (through deliberation and voting). These concepts differ in the possibility of using a direct or representative form of democratic governance and in the degree of activity of citizens in the state. What these concepts have in common is the belief that various properties of new environments, such as interactivity, faster ways of transmitting information, the ability of a large number of users to communicate with each other, an abundance of information and new capabilities of users for process management, can positively influence status policies.

More than 40 years ago, Simon Nora and Alain Minc, authors of the report "Computerization of society" to the French president, wrote: "Computerization is not only a technical innovation in recent years, but is a generalizing factor that catalyzes other factors". Information processing and storage takes place digitally, leading to systemic change in organizations and society as a whole". [8] Anticipating the advent of the Internet, the authors wrote "about the creation of a new fundamental system that denigrates literally all structures of society". A system that, unlike electricity, does not carry an inert current, but information, ie "power". Obviously, computerization affects almost all areas of life, the person, and society. This also applies to state institutions, including the ideology of the modern state on which they are based. It is mainly about the regime of government: democracy. The indicator of the degree of democracy in the state is the way in which power is organized, the techniques and methods of its implementation, ie the parameters according to which a political regime can be classified as democratic. E-government is an indispensable element of democracy. The principles of e-government include trust and security. The Republic of Moldova has made impressive progress in implementing information society technologies:

- One of two citizens is an Internet user;
- More than half of households have at least one computer, most connected households have broadband internet access;
- The country ranks according to the speed of internet access among the ten most advanced countries in the world;
- The biometric passport is implemented;
- E-Declarations system;
- Digital map.

The Republic of Moldova has joined the "Open Government Data" initiative, the "e-Government Transformation" project is underway. [7]

Table 1: Households equipment with durable goods, by area, in 2019

Source: Anuarul statistic al Republicii Moldova = Статистический ежегодник Республики Молдова = Statistical Yearbook of the Republic of Moldova, 2020 (2020). p. 111

The conceptual framework of public administration reform was formed based on the commitments that the Republic of Moldova has assumed by signing the Association Agreement between the Republic of Moldova and the European Union [5], as well as the Sustainable

Development Goals [4], National strategy for the development of the information society "Digital Moldova 2020". [3]

However, in international rankings the country is not among the advanced economies in this field, and the level and speed of development of the information society do not meet the requirements of today's international environment, in which the world is becoming increasingly "hyperconnected and digitized." The advantages of digital technologies, which people could benefit as citizens-consumers are diminished in many countries, including the Republic of Moldova, security and privacy issues, insufficient Internet access, low functionality, lack of skills necessary or accessibility of services.

The digitization of services provided by state institutions has been a cross-cutting goal, aimed at simplifying the relationship between citizen and state, eliminating unnecessary roads and queues at counters, reducing time to resolve citizen requests and, last but not least, facilitating employee activity. We can draw some of the most important directions:

E-Government – streamlining public services provided, such as: M-Cloud Joint Government Technology Platform; Government Electronic Payments Service; Government Interoperability Platform; Paperless Government Initiative - SIGEDIA; Government e-Reporting Platform; e-Procurement; e-Constructions; e-Justice; Digitization of Operational Support Systems for Government; Government Data Storage Infrastructure.

E-Culture – capitalizing on the IT potential in the process of digitizing cultural heritage, in order to increase the accessibility of cultural resources, with the main goal of digitizing cultural heritage using current, modern IT technologies, so that national cultural heritage can be preserved, promoted and transmitted to future generations.

In this sense, an essential contribution has the National Book Chamber of the Republic of Moldova (CNCRM), having the mission to manage the national documentary heritage (legal deposit) of publications (books, periodicals, manuscripts, old books, incunabula, maps, photographs, microfilms, photocopies, audio-visual materials and electronic resources) and the promotion of publishing production in the Republic of Moldova for the whole community, digitized the "Basarabiana" collection (documents dating from the 15th century - early 20th century), the collection "National Bibliography", section "Books (1924 - present)". The printed national heritage currently has about 1.5 million documents, half of which are digitized.

Some of the transformations needed for the digitization process were made even in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, which accelerated the digitization process. The situation created by the epidemiological context, determined the acceleration of the steps for the digitization of some public services offered to individuals and legal entities or internal work processes. Thus, the Certificate of systematization of publications for VAT exemption [1] issued by CNCRM is issued in electronic format being secured by electronic signature, another indispensable tool for national security.

The basic document that provides for the creation and implementation of a cyber security management system of the Republic of Moldova is the National Cyber Security Program of the Republic of Moldova for the years 2016-2020 (GD 811/2015). The program aims to create a cyber security management system of the Republic of Moldova by securing information society services, thus contributing to the development of a knowledge-based economy, which, in turn, will stimulate increased economic competitiveness and social cohesion, as well as ensuring the creation of new jobs. For the implementation of the Cyber Security Program, the Government Decision on the approval of the Mandatory Minimum Cyber Security Requirements (GD 201/2017) was elaborated and approved.

The concept of information security, approved by Law No. 299/2017, is a policy document that integrates the central areas and associated with the information space, provides notions, defines the principles of organization at state, society and individual level and details legal, technical and organizational methods, economic and counter-informative, for ensuring the information security of the Republic of Moldova. In order to achieve the Concept, the Information Security Strategy of the Republic of Moldova for 2019-2024 and the Action Plan for its implementation (HP 257/2018)

were developed and approved, the purpose of which is to correlate and systemically integrate priority areas with responsibilities and competencies to ensure information security at national level.

The rapid development of the Internet and other technologies has given rise to a new economic sector, as well as a new and rapid flow of digital information, products, and services. Although this development contributes considerably to the growth of the national economy, it also has a negative side, which is manifested by the distribution of illegal and harmful content, and behaviours that are especially dangerous for the most vulnerable among people, namely children and adolescents.

Children are increasingly exposed to the dangers of digital space, through a growing range of devices and from an early age. Therefore, it is necessary to develop their special content and services. Thus, in order to ensure online safety for children and ensure more efficient use of the Internet by them was developed and approved by Government Decision No. 212/2017 Action Plan to promote Internet safety of children and adolescents for 2017-2020.

A key question in assessing the role of information technology for democracy is how much governments and civil society learn to use the opportunities offered by new information and communication channels to promote and strengthen grassroots representative institutions that bring citizens and the state together. In this respect, the opportunities for public participation created by the new technology are certainly important, but the Internet can generate information, increasing transparency, openness, and accountability of authorities at national and international level, and strengthening interactive communication channels between citizens and intermediaries. These are special functions, and the Internet performs some of them better than any other means of communication. In particular, the Internet could:

- To provide more appropriate means of interaction in political campaigns for minority parties than traditional media (newspapers, radio, television);
- To provide greater simultaneous access to information for journalists to official documents and current legislative initiatives and proposals;
- To contribute to the consolidation of the internal organization of the parties and the interaction of the party members, etc.

Issues associated with the dangers and risks of e-democracy should not be left without scientific analysis, in particular:

- The danger of manipulating voting and election data due to a lack of sufficient data protection;
- The danger of dividing society into those who have information and those who do not (digital division) and, as a result, the violation of the principle of democracy of choice;
- The danger of propaganda by criminal and extremist groups and their influence, especially on the young generation.

As trends in the national and global economy are geared towards information management through information systems, information is becoming the most important asset, both in public institutions and in private organizations. From this perspective, special attention should be paid to information security issues. In the conditions of information, management that require greater protection and security, the management and control of the outsourcing of services is a determining factor in the organization of IT activities. From this perspective, the lack of a managerial approach to information security issues is a risk factor to ensure the confidentiality of information and the security of the components of the information system of institutions. Endangering information security can affect the ability to provide services, lead to fraud or destruction of data, breach of contractual clauses, disclosure of state secrets and confidential information, undermine the credibility of public institutions and organizations, etc.

The specific methods of protection of current information technology are varied, depending on the type of vulnerabilities they protect. Information security is an essential component of the information society, which is why specific international standards are being created. It should also be remembered that the security of information distributed on computer networks is not only a

matter of technology, but also a human and managerial issue. Lack of security and confidentiality of information has undesirable effects on the confidentiality of personal life or can lead to significant material loss, dissemination of content dangerous to public morality, social ethics, or individual security. Therefore, the desire is to achieve increasingly advanced security technologies, which make it increasingly difficult to exploit technological vulnerabilities.

Finally it may be concluded that digitization leads to important socio-cultural, economic and political changes. These changes create new opportunities, but they also create problems and challenges for people. Digitization can be expensive, but the long-term benefits of innovative solutions are clear. Digital development is driven by supranational, national and regional digital policies and supported by national security agendas. This policy is intended to accelerate overall economic growth and protect critical information infrastructure and information security, but does not address the interests, needs and concerns of individuals and communities facing digitisation in their daily lives. The aim is to bring human security issues to the cyber security agenda in order to better understand the social changes brought about by digitisation.

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